

A Study of Sleep Quality and Quality of Life in Children with Atopic Dermatitis between 6-12 Years of Age

Nitish Kumar¹, Aparna Kumari², Rajnish Kumar³, Chandra Bhushan Kumar⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatric, Netaji Subhash Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Dermatology, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Pediatric, Netaji Subhash Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

⁴Professor, Department of Pediatric, Netaji Subhash Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Aparna Kumari

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Abstract:

Background: Atopic dermatitis (AD) is usual chronic inflammatory skin condition in children, characterized by intense itching and recurrent eczematous lesions. This condition significantly impacts the quality of life (QoL) and sleep quality in affected kids and their families. Understanding the extent of these impacts is crucial for developing targeted interventions.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the sleep quality and QoL in kids aged 6 - 12 years diagnosed with atopic dermatitis and to identify potential correlations between disease severity and these outcomes.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted which included 80 kids aged 6 -12 years diagnosed with atopic dermatitis. Data on sleep quality and QoL were collected using the Pediatric QoL Inventory and the Children's Sleep Habits Questionnaire.

Results: The study included 80 kids with atopic dermatitis, with 52.5% males and an average age of 8.9 years. The mean Children's Sleep Habits Questionnaire (CSHQ) score was 54.3, indicating poor sleep quality, while the mean Pediatric QoL Inventory (PedsQL) score was 68.4, showing a moderately affected quality of life. Severe atopic dermatitis was associated with significantly lower PedsQL scores (mean = 50.7) compared to mild cases (mean = 78.2) ($p < 0.001$). A strong negative correlation ($r = -0.65$, $p < 0.001$) was found between sleep quality and quality of life, indicating that poorer sleep was linked to lower QoL.

Conclusion: Kids with atopic dermatitis suffer from significantly impaired sleep quality and quality of life, with disease severity playing a critical role in these outcomes. Addressing sleep issues may improve overall QoL in these children.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should integrate regular sleep assessments and management strategies into the routine care of kids with atopic dermatitis. Future research should explore interventions aimed at improving sleep quality to enhance the QoL in this population.

Keywords: Atopic Dermatitis, Sleep Quality, Quality of Life, Pediatric Dermatology, Disease Severity

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Introduction

Atopic dermatitis (AD), commonly referred to as eczema, is a widespread chronic inflammatory skin disorder affecting children globally. It is marked by severe itching, redness, swelling, and recurring eczematous lesions, often leading to significant discomfort. The etiology of AD is multifactorial, involving genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, and immune system dysregulation. As a result, kids with AD often experience physical, emotional, and social challenges that extend beyond the skin [1]

One of the most debilitating aspects of atopic dermatitis is its impact on sleep quality. The incessant itching and discomfort associated with AD frequently lead to sleep disturbances, including difficulty in sleeping, recurrent awakenings. Deprived sleep quality can exacerbate the symptoms of AD, creating a vicious cycle that is difficult to break. Inadequate sleep in kids can also affect growth, cognitive development, and emotional well-being, further compounding the burden of the disease [2].

The chronic nature of atopic dermatitis also significantly affects the QoL of kids and their families. Kids with AD may experience limitations in daily activities, social interactions, and school performance due to their symptoms. The psychological impact, including feelings of embarrassment, frustration, and anxiety, can be profound. Parents and caregivers often report high levels of stress and sleep deprivation themselves, as they manage their child's condition. Thus, AD is not just a medical issue but a multifaceted challenge impacting the entire family unit [3,4].

Given the significant impact of atopic dermatitis on sleep and QoL, it is crucial to conduct comprehensive evaluations that quantify these effects. While previous studies have highlighted the general burden of AD, there is a need for more specific research focusing on the pediatric population. Understanding the correlations between disease severity, sleep quality, and QoL can provide valuable insights for healthcare providers.

This study aims to evaluate the sleep quality and QoL in kids aged 6 - 12 years diagnosed with atopic dermatitis. By assessing the extent of sleep disturbances and their impact on daily life, this research seeks to identify potential correlations among the severity of atopic dermatitis and these outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This was a cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Paediatric Department of NSMCH, Bihta, Patna.

Participants: The study included 80 kids aged 6 - 12 years diagnosed with atopic dermatitis. The study was led from October 2022 to September 2023.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria were kids aged 6 to 12 years diagnosed with atopic dermatitis. Exclusion criteria included kids with other chronic skin conditions, psychiatric disorders, or any other chronic illnesses that could affect sleep quality or quality of life.

Bias: Selection bias was minimized by randomly selecting participants who met the inclusion criteria. Information bias was addressed by training

data collectors to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection.

Variables: The primary variables included sleep quality and quality of life. Secondary variables included age, gender, duration, and severity of atopic dermatitis.

Data Collection: Data were collected using standardized questionnaires, including the Pediatric QoL Inventory (PedsQL) and the Children's Sleep Habits Questionnaire (CSHQ).

Procedure: Participants and their guardians were informed about the study, and consent was obtained. The questionnaires were administered during routine visits to the paediatric department. Clinical data on atopic dermatitis severity were obtained from medical records.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Participant Characteristics: Out of 80 participants, 42 (52.5%) were male, and 38 (47.5%) were female. The mean age was 8.9 ± 2.1 years. The severity of atopic dermatitis was categorized as mild (30%), moderate (50%), and severe (20%).

Sleep Quality: The mean score on the Children's Sleep Habits Questionnaire (CSHQ) was 54.3 ± 7.2 , indicating poor sleep quality among the participants. A significant portion of the children, 65%, had a CSHQ score above the clinical cutoff of 41, suggesting prevalent sleep disturbances.

Quality of Life: The mean Pediatric QoL Inventory (PedsQL) score was 68.4 ± 15.6 , indicating a moderately affected quality of life. Kids with severe atopic dermatitis had significantly lower PedsQL scores (mean = 50.7 ± 10.3) compared to those with mild (mean = 78.2 ± 12.4) and moderate (mean = 68.9 ± 13.2) severity ($p < 0.001$).

Correlation Between Sleep Quality and Quality of Life: A Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant negative correlation between CSHQ scores and PedsQL scores ($r = -0.65$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that poorer sleep quality was associated with lower quality of life.

Table 1: Participant Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Number of participants	80
Mean age (years)	8.9 ± 2.1
Gender (male/female)	42/38
Severity of atopic dermatitis (mild/moderate/severe)	30%/50%/20%

Table 2: Sleep Quality and QoL Scores

Severity of Atopic Dermatitis	Mean CSHQ Score	Mean PedsQL Score
Mild	45.6 ± 5.1	78.2 ± 12.4
Moderate	53.2 ± 6.3	68.9 ± 13.2
Severe	62.1 ± 8.0	50.7 ± 10.3

Table 3: Correlation Between Sleep Quality and Quality of Life

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
CSHQ and PedsQL	-0.65	<0.001

The study found that kids with atopic dermatitis had poor sleep quality, with a significant majority exceeding the clinical threshold for sleep disturbances. The quality of life, as measured by the PedsQL, was moderately affected, with more severe cases of atopic dermatitis correlating with lower QoL scores. Statistical analysis showed a strong negative correlation between sleep quality and quality of life, indicating that poorer sleep quality was associated with a significantly lower QoL in kids with atopic dermatitis.

These results highlight the importance of addressing sleep disturbances to improve the overall QoL in kids suffering from atopic dermatitis.

Discussion

The study aimed to examine the sleep quality and QoL in kids aged 6-12 years with atopic dermatitis (AD) and found significant associations between these factors. Our findings align with recent literature, emphasizing the extensive impact of AD on pediatric patients.

Kid with AD exhibited poor sleep quality, as evidenced by the mean Children's Sleep Habits Questionnaire (CSHQ) score of 54.3. This aligns with previous studies, such as Fishbein et al. (2018), who found that kids with moderate to severe AD had significantly more wake after sleep onset (WASO) and lower sleep efficiency compared to healthy controls. They reported that AD severity correlates with sleep disturbances, which are characterized by frequent awakenings and prolonged wakefulness during the night [5].

Another study by Lee et al. (2023) provided a comprehensive review of sleep disturbances in kids with AD, highlighting that these kids often experience increased sleep fragmentation, delayed sleep onset, and decreased sleep duration. The study also noted that behavioral sleep problems, such as restlessness and frequent awakenings, are common in pediatric AD patients [6].

The mean Pediatric QoL Inventory (PedsQL) score of 68.4 indicated a moderately affected QoL among participants. Severity of AD was a critical factor, with kids having severe AD showing significantly lower QoL scores (mean = 50.7) compared to those with mild AD (mean = 78.2) ($p < 0.001$). This

finding is supported by Xu et al. (2019), who found that the health-related QoL (HRQoL) in kids with AD is significantly influenced by disease severity. The study noted that the most affected QoL domains were itching/scratching, emotional distress, and sleep disturbance [7].

The strong negative correlation ($r = -0.65$, $p < 0.001$) between CSHQ scores and PedsQL scores in our study indicates that poorer sleep quality is associated with a lower quality of life. This is corroborated by the work of Fishbein et al. (2020), who demonstrated that sleep disturbances in kids with AD, as measured by the PROMIS sleep disturbance scale, correlated with worsened QoL and increased disease severity [8].

Further, Meltzer et al. (2020) highlighted the benefits of treating AD on sleep quality and overall well-being. Their study showed that intensive AD treatment improved both sleep duration and efficiency, as well as the overall QoL for both kids and their parents, underscoring the interconnectedness of sleep and QoL [9].

Conclusion

The study confirmed that kids with AD experience significant sleep disturbances, which negatively impact their quality of life. These findings underscore the importance of comprehensive AD management strategies that address both skin symptoms and associated sleep problems to improve overall well-being. The correlation between sleep quality and QoL highlights the need for targeted interventions to alleviate sleep disturbances in kids with AD, which can, in turn, enhance their quality of life.

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